

JOURNAL OF AVIAN BIOLOGY

Research article

Productivity drives the dynamics of a red kite source population that depends on immigration

Thomas Pfeiffer¹ and Michael Schaub^{1,2} ²

¹Rosenweg 1, Weimar, Germany

²Schweizerische Vogelwarte, Sempach, Switzerland

Correspondence: Michael Schaub (michael.schaub@vogelwarte.ch)

Journal of Avian Biology

2023: e02984

doi: [10.1111/jav.02984](https://doi.org/10.1111/jav.02984)

Subject Editor: Blandine Doligez

Editor-in-Chief: Staffan Bensch

Accepted 14 November 2022

Local population dynamics are driven by local processes such as temporal variation of productivity, survival, emigration and population stage structure, and by processes originating from outside the local population, such as immigration. Populations may operate as sources that contribute more individuals than have died or as sinks that depend on neighbouring populations. Knowing demographic processes driving the dynamics of a local population and the significance of a local population in a system of multiple populations is crucial for understanding population dynamics and requires detailed demographic analyses. We studied demographic drivers in a red kite *Milvus milvus* population located in Germany that was monitored for 34 years using integrated population modelling. We specified the model in such a way that the numbers of experienced breeders, local recruits, locally born non-breeders and immigrants are estimated explicitly, applied a retrospective perturbation analysis to identify the demographic drivers and assessed the source-sink status of the population. The study population increased on average by 1% per year. The number of breeders was about double than the number of locally born non-breeders, and the number of experienced breeders exceeded the number of local recruits and immigrants by a factor of six to nine. The retrospective analysis identified productivity, i.e. the number of fledglings per breeding pair, as the main demographic driver, followed by adult survival and immigration. As other studies show close links between food supply and productivity, it is likely that food supply plays a critical role in red kite population dynamics. The study population contributed more individuals than it lost through mortality, but due to emigration of locally born individuals it was not self-sustainable and depended on immigration. This quantifies the population as a dependent source and shows that red kite populations are linked across large spatial scales.

Keywords: elasticity, integrated population model, *Milvus milvus*, non-breeders, population composition, retrospective perturbation analysis, source-sink status

www.avianbiology.org

© 2022 The Authors. Journal of Avian Biology published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd on behalf of Nordic Society Oikos

This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Introduction

Temporal changes of the size of a population are driven by the temporal variability of the demographic rates and of the age or stage structure of the population (Ezard et al. 2010, Koons et al. 2016). To diagnose demographic causes of past population changes and to predict future population dynamics, the understanding of how temporal variation in these components affects population changes is crucial. Their impact on the variability of population growth rate, and in turn on population dynamics, depends on how sensitive the population growth rate is to changes in these components and on how much they fluctuate temporally (Caswell 2000, Hilde et al. 2020).

Growth rate sensitivities are strongly affected by life history strategy. Long-lived species are particularly sensitive to changes in adult survival and short-lived species to changes in recruitment (Stearns 1983, Gaillard et al. 1989, Sæther and Bakke 2000, Stahl and Oli 2006, Morris et al. 2008). Demographic rates typically vary temporally as a result of variable environmental conditions such as food supply and due to density-dependent effects (Hone and Sibly 2002, Fay et al. 2015), but conclusions about the magnitude of temporal variability are less general. Because the strength of selection operating on demographic rates is related to growth rate sensitivities (Lande 1982), the demographic rates with high growth rate sensitivities tend to show little temporal variability (Morris et al. 2008). However, evidence for such demographic buffering is not general (Rotella et al. 2012, Hilde et al. 2020). Since the contribution of a demographic rate to the variability of the population growth rate is the product of its growth rate sensitivity and its temporal variability and covariability with other demographic rates, it is difficult to make predictions about the contributions of the different rates. Often it appears that fluctuations of animal populations are more strongly driven by the variability of recruitment than of adult survival (Gaillard et al. 2000, Robinson et al. 2014), but contrasting results have also been found (Reid et al. 2004, Schorcht et al. 2009).

These findings about the drivers of population dynamics were obtained under the assumption of populations having a stable stage structure. Yet, due to temporal variability in demographic rates, most populations remain in a steady transient state, i.e. they have no stable stage population structure and are therefore affected by the temporal variation of population stage structure as well (Hastings 2004, Ezard et al. 2010, Gamelon et al. 2014). Asymptotic analyses are therefore only partially successful in determining the drivers of population dynamics. Recently, Koons et al. (2016) introduced a series of retrospective perturbation analyses that focus on the realized population growth rate to assess demographic and structural drivers of past population dynamics. So far this novel approach has rarely been applied and mostly to short-lived species (Koons et al. 2017, Paquet et al. 2019, Rotelli et al. 2021, Tenan et al. 2021). Results indicate little impact of the variability of population stage structure on population dynamics. Long-lived species with delayed recruitment are

composed of an important fraction of non-breeding individuals and are therefore highly structured. Simulations suggest that the variability of population stage structure is more important for population dynamics in long- than in short-lived species (Koons et al. 2016).

Spatially structured populations typically exchange individuals, and the dynamics of the local populations are not only affected by local conditions, but also by the magnitude and direction of dispersing individuals. A local population may be a sink that can persist due to an excess of immigrants, a source that can export individuals to other populations or a combination of both (Hixon et al. 2002). Knowing how dispersal affects the local dynamics (i.e. whether source or sink) is not only important for conservation (Schaub et al. 2010, Hernandez-Matias et al. 2013, Weegman et al. 2016), but it also adds to the understanding of population dynamics beyond the local scale. A reliable assessment of the source–sink status of an open population requires detailed demographic information that is often not available and consequently few empirical examples exist (Runge et al. 2006, Furrer and Pasinelli 2016, Heinrichs et al. 2019).

Here we studied the dynamics of a population of red kites *Milvus milvus*, a diurnal raptor species endemic to Europe (Knott et al. 2009, Aebischer and Scherler 2021). Red kites are long-lived, recruitment mostly occurs at the age of 2–4 years (Aebischer and Scherler 2021) with the result that an important part of the population is composed of non-breeders (Katzenberger et al. 2021). We developed an integrated population model (Besbeas et al. 2002, Schaub and Kéry 2022) that jointly analyses multiple demographic data sets to estimate the mean and the temporal variability of demographic rates and of the numbers of breeders, non-breeders and immigrants (i.e. population stage structure). We also analysed temporal variation in nestling condition to test whether it was related with productivity, i.e. the number of nestlings produced per nest. We then computed the sensitivity of the population growth rate to changes in demographic rates and in population stage structure and performed retrospective perturbation analyses to assess how much the variability of demographic rates and of components of population stage structure have contributed to the population dynamics. We expected that the variability of population stage structure contributed significantly to the variation of the population growth rate (Koons et al. 2016). Finally, we studied whether the local red kite population operated as a sink or a source, hence assessed its role in the meta-population formed beyond the studied population.

Material and methods

Study species

The red kite is a large raptor (850–1200 g) that shows increasing populations in many parts of Europe, but regionally contrasting population trends (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, BirdLife International 2021). Red kites occupy semi-open landscapes where they search for food in agricultural

and urban areas and opportunistically feed on a broad range of food such as voles, birds, earth worms, insects and carrion (Aebischer and Scherler 2021). Red kites construct an open nest on trees in forest edges or large hedges. Once they have started reproducing, they are often faithful to the chosen territory (Newton et al. 1989). Red kites raise one brood per year comprising 1–4 nestlings and broods that failed are usually not replaced. The condition of the nestlings as well as their number per brood depends on the amount of food that they receive (Catitti et al. 2022, Nägeli et al. 2022). Despite red kites are opportunistic scavengers, their productivity shows a link with vole density (Gottschalk et al. 2015). Many red kites spend the winter season on the Iberian Peninsula, but there is large flexibility in migration behaviours. More southern populations tend to be resident, and older individuals are more likely to become resident (S. Witcak pers. comm.). Red kites from our study area are mostly migratory and spend the winter in Spain (Pfeiffer and Meyburg 2009).

Data sampling

The study was conducted in an area of about 600 km² near Weimar (50°59'N, 11°19'E, Thuringia, Germany, Supporting information) during 34 years from 1985 to 2018; the study population belongs to an area with the highest kite densities in Germany (Grüneberg and Karthäuser 2019). Every year new breeding locations were searched by visual observation of potentially breeding red kites, i.e. on trees in wood edges or rows. As the study area was visited since 1983, the location of most breeding pairs was already known when the data sampling for the current study started. All known and potential nest locations were surveyed several times per year to determine whether they were occupied and to record brood size and the number of fledglings. From a total of 1482 surveyed broods, the numbers of fledglings were exactly known from 1301 broods, because the nest was climbed to ring the nestlings or because of a good view to the nest from an elevated position. The fledglings of the remaining 181 broods were counted from the ground and it was not clear whether all of them were visible. The recorded number was therefore a minimum.

The red kite nestlings from the climbed nests were measured (wing length, body mass (starting in year 1989)) and marked with an ordinary ring (n=1946). From year 2007 onwards a total of 568 nestlings was marked in addition with wing tags that were fixed with steel wire. Finally, GPS transmitters (type SKUA-H, Ecotone) were fixed on 13 nestlings in 2017. A total of 80 breeding adults were caught from year 2002 onwards with mist nets and the help of an eagle owl that was placed close to the nest. All these birds were marked with a ring and with either a transmitter (n=62, since 2002, either from Microwave Telemetry Inc. or from e-obs GmbH) or a wing tag (n=18, since 2007). The marked individuals could be reencountered with different techniques. First, all the marked individuals could have been found dead either in the study area or elsewhere. Second, the individuals marked with a transmitter or a wing tag could be reencountered alive in the study area during the breeding period, defined as the

span between 20 March and 31 August. For each of these observations it was noted whether the individual was breeding (defined by the occupation of a nest) in the corresponding year. The numbers of reencounters are summarized in the Supporting information.

To increase the information about survival and recovery probabilities we also used ring-recovery data compiled by the Beringungszentrale Hiddensee from the period 1985 to 2018. A total of 23 093 red kites have been ringed by many ringers throughout the former eastern Germany (Supporting information). Most of these data refers to juveniles, but a small number of 1-year-old and adult individuals were also marked (Supporting information). Some individuals were marked in addition with a wing tag and the dead recoveries they produced were used for our analyses. Conversely, all the live resightings were excluded because they were not obtained under a regular sampling design. All used encounter data of the marked individuals were compiled at an annual interval with the annual divide being 15 May.

Integrated population model

We developed an integrated population model (Besbeas et al. 2002, Schaub and Abadi 2011, Kéry and Schaub 2012, Zipkin and Saunders 2018, Schaub and Kéry 2022) to analyze the data sets jointly. The core of the developed model is a state-space model, whose state-process model corresponds to a stochastic stage-structured population model and whose observation model links the observed with the estimated number of breeding pairs. The model is female based (i.e. only the females are included in the model, while assuming that the nestling sex ratio is even and the demographic rates are the same in both sexes), refers to a pre-breeding census and contains a total of eight stages, defined by age, breeding and dispersal status (below). The stage-specific numbers of individuals in a given year are determined by the stage-specific numbers in the preceding year and the year-specific demographic rates, modeled using Poisson and binomial distributions. Hence the model includes environmental as well as demographic stochasticity. The population model is described by the following eight stochastic relationships:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{1,t+1} &\sim \text{Pois}\left(\frac{f_t}{2} s_{1,t} v (N_{2,t} + N_{4,t} + N_{6,t} + b_t N_{7,t} + N_{8,t})\right) \\
 N_{2,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{2,t} \alpha_{1,t}, N_{1,t}) \\
 N_{3,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{2,t} (1 - \alpha_{1,t}), N_{1,t}) \\
 N_{4,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{3,t} \alpha_{2,t}, N_{3,t}) \\
 N_{5,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{3,t} (1 - \alpha_{2,t}), N_{3,t}) \\
 N_{6,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{3,t}, N_{3,t}) \\
 N_{7,t+1} &\sim \text{Bin}(s_{3,t}, (N_{2,t} + N_{4,t} + N_{6,t} + N_{7,t} + N_{8,t})) \\
 N_{8,t+1} &\sim \text{Pois}((N_{2,t} + N_{4,t} + N_{6,t} + b_t N_{7,t} + N_{8,t}) \omega_t)
 \end{aligned}$$

where s refers to annual survival, f to productivity, α to recruitment probability, b to breeding propensity of experienced breeders, v to site fidelity of 1-year-old individuals, ω to immigration rate and N are the stage-specific population sizes, with the first subscript denoting stage class and the second one the year (see Table 1 and Supporting information for definitions). We assume in this model that all 4-years-old individuals start reproducing if they have not reproduced so far. To relax this assumption, we also fitted a model where full reproduction was delayed to 5-years-old individuals. The parameter estimates were very similar for the two models (full reproduction delayed to 4- or 5-years-old individuals, results not presented here). For this reason, we show here only the more parsimonious model (full reproduction when 4 years old). Site fidelity of individuals older than 1 year was assumed to be 1, while site fidelity of 1-year-old individuals was estimated (v). Hence, we allowed for natal dispersal to sites outside of the study area but assumed absence of breeding dispersal. Breeding red kites rarely change territories, and if so, covered distances are short (Newton et al. 1989).

The data sets on the marked individuals and on the reproductive success were analysed with different sub-models (multistate capture-recapture models and Poisson regression models). A detailed description of the integrated population model is provided in the Supporting information.

Because we were interested in the temporal dynamics of the demographic rates and how they had contributed to population dynamics, we specified the annual deviations around a long-term mean as temporal random effects for most of the demographic rates. Moreover, we assumed that survival of the different age classes might be correlated across time because variable environmental conditions might affect survival of individuals from all age classes. Similarly, we assumed that parameters related to reproduction such as productivity, age-specific recruitment and breeding propensity to be temporally correlated. By using multivariate normal distributions these correlations were estimated in the integrated population model. Site fidelity was assumed to be constant over time because of the small amount of data on this process. Finally, immigration was modelled with an independent temporal random effect.

We fitted the models in the Bayesian framework using vague priors (Supporting information) in software JAGS (Plummer 2017) that was run from R (www.r-project.org) via package jagsUI (Kellner 2021). The fit of the model was assessed with posterior predictive checks (Schaub and Kéry 2022). We

generally present the posterior means of parameter estimates and the limits of the 95% credible intervals (CRI). Code for all analyses is provided in the Supporting information.

Prospective and retrospective perturbation analyses

We studied the effects of the temporal variation of demographic rates on population growth. A temporal change in a demographic rate can have a direct, immediate effect on population growth rate and an indirect, delayed effect channeled through changes in population stage structure over time. We first assessed how sensitive the population growth rate is to changes in demographic rates and in population stage structure by calculating elasticities (prospective perturbation analysis, Caswell 2000, Koons et al. 2017). Second, we applied a retrospective population analysis (Koons et al. 2016, 2017; chapter 9 in Schaub and Kéry 2022) to quantify how much the temporal variability of demographic rates (direct effects) and of population stage structure (indirect effects) had contributed to the temporal variability of the realized population growth rate. We included the estimated uncertainties of demographic rates and of population stage structure in these assessments (Schaub and Kéry 2022).

Nestling condition

We aged red kite nestlings when they were ringed based on their wing length (Traue and Wuttky 1966) as wing growth is weakly impacted by nutrition, disease and parasites (Mammen and Stubbe 1995). We calculated an annual index of nestling condition as the mean proportional deviation of the body mass of a given nestling to the average body mass of a nestling of the same age in the years 1989–1994. Since body mass measurements of nestlings started in 1989 only, the sample size was 1756 individuals from 806 broods. We fitted a linear model to these data with year and nest identification number as random effects, the latter accounting for non-independence of nestlings from the same nest. We correlated the annual index of nestling condition with annual estimates of productivity to assess whether they are related.

Source–sink status

To assess the source–sink status of the studied red kite population, we computed its per capita contribution to its own and to neighboring populations (C^r metrics) and its per

Table 1. Definition of the symbols of the stage-specific population sizes used in the integrated population model.

Symbol	Definition
$N_{1,t}$	Locally born, philopatric, not yet recruited, 1-year-old individuals in year t
$N_{2,t}$	Locally born, 2-years-old first-time breeders in year t
$N_{3,t}$	Locally born, not yet recruited, 2-years-old individuals in year t
$N_{4,t}$	Locally born, 3-years-old first-time breeders in year t
$N_{5,t}$	Locally born, not yet recruited, 3-years-old individuals in year t
$N_{6,t}$	Locally born, 4-years-old first-time breeders in year t
$N_{7,t}$	Experienced breeders in year t
$N_{8,t}$	Immigrants (not locally born individuals that breed for the first time in the population in year t)

capita self-recruitment rate (R^* metrics, Runge et al. 2006). If the contribution metric is > 1 , the population contributed more individuals than it lost by mortality and operated a source. By contrast, if $C < 1$, the population lost more individuals than it has contributed and was a sink. The self-recruitment rate expresses whether the population was self-sustainable ($R^* > 1$), or whether it depended on immigration ($R^* < 1$), and hence allows further specification about the type of population (Hixon et al. 2002). We calculated both metrics following Runge et al. (2006) by using the means of the demographic rates (see Supporting information for code). Hence, our assessment refers to an average across the study period. We included the uncertainties in the parameter estimates for the calculations.

Results

Population development and demographic rates

All parameters of our model converged well and most of the posterior predictive checks were consistent with the data indicating that reliable inference from the model estimates was possible (Supporting information). The estimated number of breeding pairs varied in the course of the study period between 31 and 72, and the total number of females (i.e. sum of locally born philopatric non-breeders, experienced breeders and immigrants) between 55 and 103 (Fig. 1A). The population showed a slight decline during few years before 2000, but generally increased during the study period at a mean annual rate of 1.010 (CRI: 0.999–1.023). The ratio of non-breeders to breeders varied between 0.31 and 1.09 (mean: 0.51; CRI: 0.36–0.70) across time. Hence, a red kite population of 100 breeding pairs with these features is composed of about 300 individuals (both sexes included). This is likely to be an underestimation as immigrants might be present in the population already before they reproduce for the first time. Local recruits and immigrants constituted smaller fractions of the breeders than experienced breeders; local recruits were 6.3 (CRI: 4.5–8.7) times and immigrants 8.7 (CRI: 5.0–17.4) times less frequent than experienced breeders (Fig. 1B).

Survival was lower and more temporally variable in the younger compared to the older age classes (Fig. 2A–C). Productivity showed extensive temporal fluctuations (Fig. 2D). The probability to start reproducing was higher at the age of 3 than of 2 years (Fig. 2E–F), indicating that most red kites were recruited into the breeding population at the age of 3 or 4 years. The estimation uncertainty of these parameters was pronounced, and the temporal pattern could not be assessed accurately. The breeding propensity was high (Fig. 2G), indicating that experienced breeders rarely skip a possible breeding event. There was also little temporal fluctuation in this parameter. The probability that locally born kites did not emigrate from the study population, i.e. natal philopatry, was 0.53 (CRI: 0.38–0.69). We could not study temporal variability in this parameter due

Figure 1. Estimates of the numbers of red kite females from the integrated population model. (A) Decomposition of the total into breeders and locally born non-breeders; (B) decomposition of the breeders into experienced breeders, local recruits (locally born first-time breeders) and immigrants. The dots are posterior means, the vertical lines show the limits of the 95% CRI.

to limited data availability. The immigration rate did not show strong temporal fluctuations (Fig. 2H). The estimated mean immigration rate of 0.11 corresponds to a mean proportion of immigrants among the new breeders (immigrants plus local recruits) of 0.26 (CRI: 0.12–0.38). Finally, there was no evidence of important temporal correlations between demographic rates (all correlations between -0.09 and 0.10 ; Supporting information).

Prospective and retrospective perturbation analyses

The realized population growth rate was generally more sensitive to changes in the demographic rates than to changes in population stage structure (Fig. 3A). Adult survival achieved by far the highest elasticity, followed by breeding probability and equal values for recruitment related parameters (first year survival, productivity and site fidelity), and finally by slightly smaller values for subadult survival and immigration. The potential effect of the temporal variation of the age at first reproduction must be evaluated by considering the elasticities of age-dependent probabilities of first reproduction and of age-dependent proportions of first-time breeders. They were all close to zero indicating that population growth rate was little sensitive to changes in the age of first reproduction. A

Figure 2. Estimated demographic rates (A)–(H); from the integrated population model) and index of nesting condition (I; from the linear model) from the red kite population. Shown are the annual posterior means (closed dots) with the 95% credible intervals (vertical lines) and the long-term means (horizontal broken lines) with their corresponding 95% CRI (reddish layer).

proportional increase of breeding individuals would have a positive effect on the population growth rate while a proportional increase of 1-year-old individual would have a negative effect as 1-year-old individuals do not reproduce.

The temporal variance of the realized population growth rate was 0.0118 (CRI: 0.0066–0.0186). The contributions of the temporal variabilities in demographic rates and of components of population structure summed to 0.0058 (CRI: 0.0030–0.0101), i.e. about half of the temporal variability of the realized population growth rate. The remaining variability was due to demographic stochasticity, temporal autocorrelation and unexplained variability. The contributions of the temporal variability of the demographic rates and variability in population stage structure summed to 0.0044 (CRI: 291 0.0021–0.0080) and 0.0014 (CRI: 0.0005–0.0027), respectively. Thus, the direct effects of the variability in demographic rates on population dynamics were about 3.3 times stronger than their indirect effects channelled through changes in the population stage structure.

The variability in productivity was the most important demographic driver of past population dynamics, followed by the variability in adult survival, immigration and juvenile survival (Fig. 3B). The other demographic rates contributed clearly less. The contribution of site fidelity was obviously zero because we assumed this parameter to be constant over time. The temporal variabilities of the proportion of first-year individuals and of experienced breeders were the most influential components of the population stage structure that contributed to the variability of population growth rate.

Nesting condition

The index of nesting condition fluctuated strongly (Fig. 2I) and was positively correlated with productivity ($r=0.36$; probability that the correlation was positive, $P(r > 0) = 0.99$) indicating that in years with enhanced productivity the nestlings were in better condition than in years with low productivity. The nesting condition appeared to be declining over

Figure 3. (A) Elasticity of the realized population growth rate (λ) to changes in the demographic parameters (red) and in population stage structure (blue), and (B) the relative contribution of the variability of the demographic rates (red) and of population stage structure (blue) to the temporal variability in realized population growth rate. The bars show the posterior means, the vertical lines indicate the limits of the 95% CRI. The values are calculated from the result of the integrated population model. s_1, s_2, s_3 : age-specific survival; f : productivity; α_1, α_2 : age-specific probability to start reproducing; b : breeding propensity of experienced breeders; τ : site fidelity; ω : immigration; N_1, N_3, N_5 : locally born, not recruited individuals of different ages; N_2, N_4, N_6 : locally born first-time breeders of different ages; N_7 : experienced breeders; N_8 : immigrants.

time (Fig. 2I). We fitted a further model including a temporal trend in mean nestling condition which statistically confirmed that body condition declined (probability of a decline was 1).

Source–sink status

Across all study years, the contribution metrics C was 1.083 (95% CRI: 1.005–1.171) indicating that on average the population contributed more individuals than it had lost through mortality, hence the population operated as a source. The self-recruitment rate R was less than 1 (mean: 0.939; 95% CRI: 0.897–0.984) indicating that the source population was not self-sustainable but depended on immigration. Together, these metrics qualify the local red kite population as a dependent source (Hixon et al. 2002, Runge et al. 2006).

Discussion

Despite the red kite population was composed of individuals of different ages, breeding status and origin, the direct effects of the temporal variation of the demographic rates contributed more to population dynamics than their indirect

effects channelled through the variation of the proportion of individuals in the different stages. Overall, the temporal fluctuation of productivity was the most important demographic driver of the increasing population, which produced more individuals than it lost through mortality but because of emigration was nevertheless not self-sustainable and depended on immigration.

Growth rate elasticities were in agreement with the expectation for a long-lived species (Sæther and Bakke 2000, Stahl and Oli 2006) and closely matched with findings from another red kite population (Tenan et al. 2012): the population growth rate was highly sensitive to changes in adult survival but only moderately sensitive to changes in recruitment related parameters, which all had similar elasticity values. Moreover, the growth rate was more sensitive to changes in demographic rates than to changes in population stage structure. Despite these findings characterizing the prospective dynamics of the population, the strongest driver retrospectively was productivity, followed by adult survival probability and immigration rate. Productivity contributed strongly to population dynamics due to its large temporal variability. There is empirical evidence that populations of other raptor species were driven by the variability of productivity or recruitment as well (Newton and Marquiss 1986, Houston and Schmutz 1995, Wahl and Barbraud 2014).

Simulations have shown that the expected contribution of the change in population stage structure depends on the life history (Koons et al. 2016). Fluctuations in red kite population stage structure contributed about 25% to the total variability in the population growth rate, which fits well with expectations (Koons et al. 2016). The population stage structure fluctuates because of temporal variation of the demographic rates. Hence, variabilities in the demographic rates had not only immediate effects on population dynamics, but also significant delayed effects mediated through changes in population stage structure.

Temporal variability of demographic rates

The average demographic rates from our study were similar to the rates from other red kite populations (Mougeot and Bretagnolle 2006, Tenan et al. 2012, Sanz-Aguilar et al. 2015, Katzenberger et al. 2019). Productivity varied strongly between years and nestlings were in better condition in years with enhanced productivity. Possible reasons causing temporal variability are variation in food supply (Gottschalk et al. 2015, Catitti et al. 2022, Nægeli et al. 2022), notably the availability of voles (Gottschalk et al. 2015), rainy weather (Nægeli et al. 2022) and nest predation by goshawks *Accipiter gentilis* or raccoons *Procyon lotor*, with the latter varying more in space than in time (Gottschalk et al. 2019).

Survival of all age classes varied over time and as expected the variability was stronger in younger than in older age classes (Fig. 2). Although several studies investigated mortality causes in red kites (Villafuente et al. 1998, Smart et al. 2010, Coeurdassier et al. 2012, Tavecchia et al. 2012, Molenaar et al. 2017), we are not aware of any analyses

investigating reasons for the temporal variation in survival. Survival estimates of red kites ringed throughout Germany from 1970 to 2015 based on dead recoveries showed a substantial decline for juveniles and a moderate decline for adults over time (Katzenberger et al. 2019). These declines mainly occurred between 1980 and 1995 for juvenile survival and before 1985 for adult survival. While the findings of adult survival match with our results, they differ for juvenile survival. Juvenile survival was estimated to be > 0.6 in our study and there was no indication of a decline over time, while it declined and was estimated at < 0.4 after 1990 in Katzenberger et al. (2019). The estimation of juvenile survival based on ring-recovery data of birds marked predominantly as juvenile is challenging because of weak parameter identifiability (Anderson et al. 1985). We are confident that our estimates are robust, because in addition to the dead recoveries we used life reencounters and embedded the estimation in an integrated population model that can leverage potential bias. Our estimates should therefore be representative for our study area, while those from Katzenberger et al. (2019) constitute an average across complete Germany.

The annual estimates of demographic rates other than productivity and survival had large uncertainties, masking potential temporal patterns. The reencounter data of individuals marked as juveniles are informative about the probability to start reproducing and about site fidelity, yet these data were sparse in our study. The temporal variation of the probability to start reproducing is likely more pronounced than estimated. Our annual estimates are strongly shrunken towards the common mean; the amount of shrinkage in random effects models is inversely related with sample size (Burnham and White 2002). Moreover, site fidelity of 1-year-old kites was assumed to be constant over time due to data sparseness, but in reality, it is likely to be fluctuating. Future studies on red kite population dynamics should try to obtain improved estimates of the temporal patterns of these recruitment related parameters, because the recruitment process is the least studied demographic process in the life cycle of red kites and potentially an important population driver (Katzenberger et al. 2021).

Source–sink status

Our studied red kite population operated in the long-term as a dependent source, thus it contributed more individuals than it lost through mortality but was at the same time dependent on immigration. The reason why the population was not self-sustainable is natal dispersal: only about half of the locally produced individuals recruited in the local population, the other half emigrated to other populations. A dependency of local populations on immigration and thus on neighboring populations is common in birds (Millon et al. 2019), including raptors (Altwegg et al. 2014, Millsap 2017, Reichert et al. 2021), but often it is unclear whether the focal population is a sink or a source. Here we were able to diagnose the status because all demographic processes could be estimated.

Because of dispersal, the studied red kite population is a non-independent part of a larger population system. Red kites occur more or less continuously across the landscape outside our study area, and we can only speculate about how population dynamics at larger spatial scales than the one studied here works. Given the prominent role of productivity for the local dynamics and the fact that the number of emigrants that constitute immigrants to other populations also depends on productivity, it is likely that productivity is a crucial factor for red kite population dynamics across larger spatial scales. This hypothesis is reinforced by the pronounced spatial autocorrelation of vole abundance (Fay et al. 2020) and of weather that should reduce spatial heterogeneity in red kite productivity.

It would have been interesting to study temporal changes in the source–sink status of the red kite population. Unfortunately, this was impossible due to a lack of annual estimates of emigration probabilities. The emigration probability is the complement to one of site fidelity, which was assumed to be constant due to data sparseness. Hence, improved estimates of the site fidelity of 1-year-old red kites would not only allow a better understanding of the impact of recruitment on population dynamics, but also to get insights into temporal changes of the source–sink status.

Conservation should primary focus on self-sustainable populations to ensure that local actions are successful (Hagen and Hodges 2006, Schaub and Ullrich 2021). Although the studied population has increased in the long term, the density of breeding pairs was high (0.11 breeding pairs km^{-2} in 2018) and it extended over a large area (600 km^2), it was not self-sustainable. If the demographic rates of red kites over a large area are the same as those in our study population, the self-recruitment rate would increase with increasing spatial extent of the focal population because fewer individuals end up outside the population boundaries after dispersal. At some spatial extent, such a hypothetical population will become self-sustainable, and this is the spatial scale at which conservation should focus. We do not know this spatial scale, but it is clear that it must be larger than the size of our study population. Obviously, this is a very crude assessment. Spatially explicit demographic analyses across large spatial scales would be necessary to relax the homogeneity assumption and to determine the size of a self-sustainable population with more confidence.

Food supply may be a critical driver of red kite population dynamics

Productivity and population density in raptors often have strong links to food abundance (Houston and Schmutz 1995, Salamolard et al. 2000, Rooney et al. 2015), and the red kite is no exception. Empirical studies have shown that food supply positively affects red kite productivity (Gottschalk et al. 2015), and nestling food supplementation experiments revealed that growth and condition of nestlings are reduced and their stress levels increased when food is short (Catitti et al. 2022, Nägeli et al. 2022). We found a positive

correlation between productivity and nestling condition suggesting that under high food availability, more nestlings of a nest survive, and they are in good condition. Competition among nestlings in a nest is amplified under food shortage with the result that some nestlings die, and the survivors have a worse condition. A reduced condition may have negative effects on survival after fledging as observed in other birds (Wiens et al. 2006, Perrig et al. 2014). Because the temporal variation of productivity was the main driver in the red kite population, the close link between food supply and productivity (Gottschalk et al. 2015, Nägeli et al. 2022) suggests that food supply is a critical environmental factor of the red kite population dynamics.

We observed that the nestling condition declined over time (Fig. 2I), and we suggest two not mutually exclusive explanations for this trend. First, it might be caused by a decline of overall food supply. We believe the increasing intensity of farming, which reduced the accessibility to food during the chick rearing phase, to be a possible mechanism. The study area is dominated by large arable fields (cereal, rapeseed), with only small, interspersed patches of grassland. Cereal yield per area has increased by 30% during the past decades in Germany (www.fao.org, accessed 13 March 2019) due to application of more efficient fertilizers and pesticides, and cultivation of different crop varieties. As a result, the sward structure has become denser and less soft (Wilson et al. 2005), which in turn reduced the accessibility to food on the ground (Shrubbs 1980, Aschwanden et al. 2005). Second, the overall food supply could have remained constant, but the food available for each individual had declined as a result of increasing population size. Presumably both mechanisms were working simultaneously, the overall food supply declined and the increasing population size amplified the reduction of food per individual leading to intraspecific competition for food.

Significance of non-breeders

About one third of the individuals in the population were locally born, philopatric non-breeders. Yet, the total proportion of non-breeders is presumably larger because immigrants likely prospect the area already in the years before they breed for a first time, while in our model we assumed that immigrants enter the population only in the year when they start reproducing. Non-breeders (often termed floaters) can impact population dynamics through different processes (Lopez-Sepulcre and Kokko 2005, Kokko and Sutherland 2007, Penteriani et al. 2011, Lee et al. 2017). First, they may buffer population dynamics, as non-breeders create a reservoir of mature individuals that are ready to enter immediately the breeding part of the population should the number of established breeders decline (Walters et al. 2002). Second, non-breeders may negatively affect populations, as they may try to oust breeders from their territories (Bretagnolle et al. 2008) or they may compete for food with the breeders (Carrete et al. 2006). Both behaviours can reduce productivity of breeders and might result in a density-dependent

regulation of the population. A simulation study of red kites in Germany suggests that density-dependent age at first reproduction together with the recent decline of some demographic rates (notably juvenile survival) has resulted in a shift towards younger ages at first reproduction and in an overall decline of non-breeders, but not (yet) of breeders (Katzenberger et al. 2021). In our population we have no indication of such a shift, but we acknowledge that most parameters related to recruitment are estimated with large uncertainty. Again, more research about recruitment related parameters (age-specific probability of first-time breeding, site fidelity) is needed for better insights.

Our study adds empirical evidence that non-breeders constitute an important fraction of the red kite population, that productivity was the main demographic population driver and that the increasing population depended on immigration although it extended over a large area. Further studies should be targeted to get more insights into the recruitment process because this is the least understood demographic process.

Acknowledgements – We thank Bernd-Ulrich Meyburg and Rainer Raab for their financial and logistic support regarding the transmitters, and Winfried Nachtigall and Duncan Orr-Ewing for their support regarding the wing tags. Financial support was provided by the Stiftung für Naturschutz Thüringen, the state Thüringen, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), the Dachverband Deutscher Avifaunisten (DDA) and the Naturschutzbund Deutschland e.V. (NABU). We are grateful also to all red kite ringers and detectors of marked dead and life individuals, and to Christof Herrmann from the Beringungszentrale Hiddensee for providing data on marked and recovered individuals. Rémi Fay, Martin Grüebler, Gilberto Pasinelli, Floriane Plard and Patrick Scherler provided valuable comments on the manuscript.

Funding – Bernd-Ulrich Meyburg and Rainer Raab provided financial and logistic support regarding the transmitters. Winfried Nachtigall and Duncan Orr-Ewing provided logistic support regarding the wing tags.

Permits – The licenses to catch and ring the red kites, as well as to fix wing tags and satellite transmitters were issued by the ‘Thüringer Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Naturschutz und Umwelt’, the ‘Thüringer Landesverwaltungsamt’ and by the ‘unteren Jagdbehörden der Stadt Weimar und der Kreise Weimarer Land und Sömmerda’.

Author contributions

Thomas Pfeiffer: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Project administration (lead); Resources (lead); Writing – review and editing (supporting). **Michael Schaub:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (lead).

Transparent peer review

The peer review history for this article is available at <https://publons.com/publon/10.1111/jav.02984>.

Data availability statement

Data are available from the vogelwarte.ch Open Repository and Archive: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7326871> (Pfeiffer and Schaub 2022).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

References

- Aebischer, A. and Scherler, P. 2021. Der Rotmilan: Ein Greifvogel im Aufwind. – Haupt Verlag.
- Altwegg, R., Jenkins, A. and Abadi, F. 2014. Nestboxes and immigration drive the growth of an urban peregrine falcon *Falco peregrinus* population. *Ibis* 156: 107–115.
- Anderson, D. R., Burnham, K. P. and White, G. C. 1985. Problems in estimating age-specific survival rates from recovery data of birds ringed as young. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 54: 89–98.
- Aschwanden, J., Birrer, S. and Jenni, L. 2005. Are ecological compensation areas attractive hunting sites for common kestrels *Falco tinnunculus* and long-eared owls *Asio otus*? – *J. Ornithol.* 146: 279–286.
- Besbeas, P., Freeman, S. N., Morgan, B. J. T. and Catchpole, E. A. 2002. Integrating mark–recapture–recovery and census data to estimate animal abundance and demographic parameters. – *Biometrics* 58: 540–547.
- BirdLife International 2021. European Red List of birds, Luxembourg. – BirdLife International.
- Bretagnolle, V., Mougeot, F. and Thibault, J.-C. 2008. Density dependence in a recovering osprey population: demographic and behavioural processes. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 77: 998–1007.
- Burnham, K. P. and White, G. C. 2002. Evaluation of some random effects methodology applicable to bird ringing data. – *J. Appl. Stat.* 29: 245–264.
- Carrete, M., Donazar, J. A. and Margalida, A. 2006. Density-dependent productivity depression in Pyrenean bearded vultures: implications for conservation. – *Ecol. Appl.* 16: 1674–1682.
- Caswell, H. 2000. Prospective and retrospective perturbation analyses: their roles in conservation biology. – *Ecology* 81: 619–627.
- Catitti, B., Gruebler, M. U., Kormann, U. G., Scherler, P., Witczak, S., van Bergen, V. S. and Jenni-Eiermann, S. 2022. Hungry or angry? Experimental evidence for the effects of food availability on two measures of stress in developing wild raptor nestlings. – *J. Exp. Biol.* 225: jeb244102.
- Coeurdassier, M., Poirson, C., Paul, J.-P., Rieffel, D., Michelat, D., Reymond, D., Legay, P., Giraudoux, P. and Scheifler, R. 2012. The diet of migrant red kites *Milvus milvus* during a water vole *Arvicola terrestris* outbreak in eastern France and the associated risk of secondary poisoning by the rodenticide bromadiolone. – *Ibis* 154: 136–146.
- Ezard, T. H. G., Bullock, J. M., Dalglish, H. J., Millon, A., Pelletier, F., Ozgul, A. and Koons, D. N. 2010. Matrix models for a changeable world: the importance of transient dynamics in population management. – *J. Appl. Ecol.* 47: 515–523.
- Fay, R., Michler, S., Laesser, J., Jeanmonod, J. and Schaub, M. 2020. Large-scale vole population synchrony in central Europe revealed by kestrel breeding performance. – *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 7: 512.
- Fay, R., Weimerskirch, H., Delord, K. and Barbraud, C. 2015. Population density and climate shape early-life survival and recruitment in a long-lived pelagic seabird. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 84: 1423–1433.
- Furrer, R. D. and Pasinelli, G. 2016. Empirical evidence for source–sink populations: a review on occurrence, assessments and implications. – *Biol. Rev.* 91: 782–795.
- Gaillard, J. M., Festa-Bianchet, M., Yoccoz, N. G., Loison, A. and Toigo, C. 2000. Temporal variation in fitness components and population dynamics of large herbivores. – *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* 31: 367–393.
- Gaillard, J. M., Pontier, D., Allainé, D., Lebreton, J.-D., Trouvilliez, J. and Clobert, J. 1989. An analysis of demographic tactics in birds and mammals. – *Oikos* 56: 59–76.
- Gamelon, M., Gimenez, O., Baubet, E., Coulson, T., Tuljapurkar, S. and Gaillard, J. M. 2014. Influence of life-history tactics on transient dynamics: a comparative analysis across mammalian populations. – *Am. Nat.* 184: 673–683.
- Gottschalk, E., Bayoh, R., Kamrad, M. and Wasmund, N. 2019. Sterblichkeit junger Rotmilane *Milvus milvus* im Nest – Ausmass und Ursachen. – *Vogelwelt* 139: 155–160.
- Gottschalk, E., Wasmund, N., Sauer, B. and Bayoh, R. 2015. Nahrungsmangel beim Rotmilan *Milvus milvus*? Was können zusätzliche Mahdflächen zur Nahrungsverfügbarkeit beitragen? – *Abh. Ber. Mus. Heineanum* 10: 17–32.
- Grüneberg, C. and Karthäuser, J. 2019. Verbreitung und Bestand des Rotmilans *Milvus milvus* in Deutschland – Ergebnisse der bundesweiten Kartierung 2010–2014. – *Vogelwelt* 139: 101–116.
- Hagen, A. N. and Hodges, K. E. 2006. Resolving critical habitat designation failures: reconciling law, policy and biology. – *Conserv. Biol.* 20: 399–407.
- Hastings, A. 2004. Transients: the key to long-term ecological understanding? – *Trend. Ecol. Evol.* 19: 39–45.
- Heinrichs, J. A., Walker, L. E., Lawler, J. J., Schumaker, N. H., Monroe, K. C. and Bleisch, A. D. 2019. Recent advances and current challenges in applying source–sink theory to species conservation. – *Curr. Landsc. Ecol. Rep.* 4: 51–60.
- Hernandez-Matias, A., Real, J., Moleon, M., Palma, L., Sanchez-Zapata, J. A., Pradel, R., Carrete, M., Gil-Sanchez, J. M., Beja, P., Arroyo, B., Fernandez, C., Ferreiro, E. and Garcia, J. 2013. From local monitoring to a broad-scale viability assessment: a case study for the Bonelli's eagle in western Europe. – *Ecol. Monogr.* 83: 239–261.
- Hilde, C. H., Gamelon, M., Sæther, B.-E., Gaillard, J.-M., Yoccoz, N. G. and Pélabon, C. 2020. The demographic buffering hypothesis: evidence and challenges. – *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 35: 523–538.
- Hixon, M. A., Pacala, S. W. and Sandin, S. A. 2002. Population regulation: historical context and contemporary challenges of open vs closed systems. – *Ecology* 83: 1490–1508.
- Hone, J. and Sibly, R. M. 2002. Demographic, mechanistic and density-dependent determinants of population growth rate: a case study of an avian predator. – *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. B* 357: 1171–1177.
- Houston, C. S. and Schmutz, J. K. 1995. Declining reproduction among Swainson's hawks in prairie Canada. – *J. Raptor Res.* 29: 198–201.
- Katzenberger, J., Gottschalk, E., Balkenhol, N. and Waltert, M. 2019. Long-term decline of juvenile survival in German Red Kites. – *J. Ornithol.* 160: 337–349.

- Katzenberger, J., Gottschalk, E., Balkenhol, N. and Waltert, M. 2021. Density-dependent age of first reproduction as a key factor for population dynamics: stable breeding populations mask strong floater declines in a long-lived raptor. – *Anim. Conserv.* 42: 114.
- Kellner, K. F. 2021. jagsUI: a wrapper around 'rjags' to streamline 'JAGS' analyses. – R package version 1.5.2, <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=jagsUI>.
- Kéry, M. and Schaub, M. 2012. Bayesian population analysis using WinBUGS – a hierarchical perspective. – Academic Press.
- Knott, J., Newbery, P. and Barov, B. 2009. Action plan for the red kite *Milvus milvus* in the European Union. – BirdLife International for the European Union.
- Kokko, H. and Sutherland, W. J. 2007. Optimal floating and queuing strategies: consequences for density dependence and habitat loss. – *Am. Nat.* 152: 354–366.
- Koons, D. N., Arnold, T. W. and Schaub, M. 2017. Understanding the demographic drivers of realized population growth rates. – *Ecol. Appl.* 27: 2102–2115.
- Koons, D. N., Iles, D. T., Schaub, M. and Caswell, H. 2016. A life-history perspective on the demographic drivers of structured population dynamics in changing environments. – *Ecol. Lett.* 19: 1023–1031.
- Lande, R. 1982. A quantitative genetic theory of life history evolution. – *Ecology* 63: 607–615.
- Lee, A. M., Reid, J. M. and Beissinger, S. R. 2017. Modeling effects of nonbreeders on population growth estimates. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 86: 75–87.
- Lopez-Sepulcre, A. and Kokko, H. 2005. Territorial defense, territory size and population regulation. – *Am. Nat.* 166: 317–329.
- Mammen, U. and Stubbe, M. 1995. Alterseinschätzung und Brutbeginn des Rotmilans *Milvus milvus*. – *Vogel Umwelt* 8: 91–98.
- Millon, A., Lambin, X., Devillard, S. and Schaub, M. 2019. Quantifying the contribution of immigration to population dynamics: a review of methods, evidence and perspectives in birds and mammals. – *Biol. Rev.* 94: 2049–2067.
- Millspaugh, B. A. 2017. Demography and metapopulation dynamics of an urban Cooper's hawk subpopulation *Condor* 120: 63–80.
- Molenaar, F. M., Jaffé, J. E., Carter, I., Barnett, E. A., Shore, R. F., Marcus Rowcliffe, J. and Sainsbury, A. W. 2017. Poisoning of reintroduced red kites *Milvus milvus* in England. – *Eur. J. Wildl. Res.* 63: 204.
- Morris, W. F., Pfister, C. A., Tuljapurkar, S., Haridas, C. V., Boggs, C. L., Boyce, M. S., Bruna, E. M., Church, D. R., Coulson, T., Doak, D. F., Forsyth, S., Gaillard, J.-M., Horvitz, C. C., Kalisz, S., Kendall, B. E., Knight, T. M., Lee, C. T. and Menges, E. S. 2008. Longevity can buffer plant and animal populations against changing climatic variability. – *Ecology* 89: 19–25.
- Mougeot, F. and Bretagnolle, V. 2006. Breeding biology of the red kite *Milvus milvus* in Corsica. – *Ibis* 148: 436–448.
- Nägeli, M., Scherler, P., Witzczak, S., Catitti, B., Aebischer, A., van Bergen, V., Kormann, U. and Gruebler, M. U. 2022. Weather and food availability additively affect reproductive output in an expanding raptor population. – *Oecologia* 198: 125–138.
- Newton, I. and Marquis, M. 1986. Population regulation in sparrowhawks. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 55: 463–480.
- Newton, I., Davis, P. E. and Davis, J. E. 1989. Age at first breeding, dispersal and survival of red kites *Milvus milvus* in Wales. – *Ibis* 131: 16–21.
- Paquet, M., Arlt, D., Knape, J., Low, M., Forslund, P. and Pärt, T. 2019. Quantifying the links between land use and population growth rate in a declining farmland bird. – *Ecol. Evol.* 9: 868–879.
- Penteriani, V., Ferrer, M. and Delgado, M. M. 2011. Floater strategies and dynamics in birds, and their importance in conservation biology: towards an understanding of nonbreeders in avian populations. – *Anim. Conserv.* 14: 233–241.
- Perrig, M., Gruebler, M. U., Keil, H. and Naef-Daenzer, B. 2014. Experimental food supplementation affects the physical development, behaviour and survival of little owl *Athene noctua* nestlings. – *Ibis* 156: 755–767.
- Pfeiffer, T. and Meyburg, B. U. 2009. Satellitentelemetrische Untersuchungen zum Zug- und Überwinterungsverhalten thüringischer Rotmilane *Milvus milvus*. – *Vogelwarte* 47: 171–187.
- Pfeiffer, T. and Schaub, M. 2022. Data from: Productivity drives the dynamics of a red kite source population that depends on immigration. – <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7326871>.
- Plummer, M. 2017. JAGS ver. 4.3.0 user manual, <https://sourceforge.net/projects/mcmc-jags/files/>.
- Reichert, B. E., Fletcher, R. J. and Kitchens, W. M. 2021. The demographic contributions of connectivity versus local dynamics to population growth of an endangered bird. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 90: 574–584.
- Reid, J. M., Bignal, E. M., Bignal, S., McCracken, D. I. and Monaghan, P. 2004. Identifying the demographic determinants of population growth rate: a case study of red-billed crows *Pyrrhocorax pyrrhocorax*. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 73: 777–788.
- Robinson, R. A., Morrison, C. A. and Baillie, S. R. 2014. Integrating demographic data: towards a framework for monitoring wildlife populations at large spatial scales. – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 5: 1361–1372.
- Rooney, E., Reid, N. and Montgomery, W. I. 2015. Supplementary feeding increases common buzzard *Buteo buteo* productivity but only in poor-quality habitat. – *Ibis* 157: 181–185.
- Rotella, J. J., Link, W. A., Chambert, T., Stauffer, G. E. and Garrott, R. A. 2012. Evaluating the demographic buffering hypothesis with vital rates estimated for Weddell seals from 30 years of mark-recapture data. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 81: 162–173.
- Rotelli, L., Bionda, R., Zbinden, N. and Schaub, M. 2021. Dynamics of two black grouse populations are driven by the variation of chick survival. – *Wildl. Biol.* 2021: wlb.00874.
- Runge, J. P., Runge, M. C. and Nichols, J. D. 2006. The role of local populations within a landscape context: defining and classifying sources and sinks. – *Am. Nat.* 167: 925–938.
- Sæther, B.-E. and Bakke, O. 2000. Avian life history variation and contribution of demographic traits to the population growth rate. – *Ecology* 81: 642–653.
- Salamolard, M., Butet, A., Leroux, A. and Bretagnolle, V. 2000. Responses of an avian predator to variations in prey density at a temperate latitude. – *Ecology* 81: 2428–2441.
- Sanz-Aguilar, A., Pablo, F. de and Donazar, J. A. 2015. Age-dependent survival of island vs mainland populations of two avian scavengers: delving into migration costs *Oecologia* 179: 405–414.
- Schaub, M. and Abadi, F. 2011. Integrated population models: a novel analysis framework for deeper insights into population dynamics. – *J. Ornithol.* 152: 227–237.
- Schaub, M. and Kéry, M. 2022. Integrated population models. Theory and ecological applications with R and JAGS. – Academic Press an imprint of Elsevier.
- Schaub, M. and Ullrich, B. 2021. A drop in immigration results in the extinction of a local woodchat shrike population. – *Anim. Conserv.* 24: 335–345.

- Schaub, M., Aebischer, A., Gimenez, O., Berger, S. and Arlettaz, R. 2010. Massive immigration balances high anthropogenic mortality in a stable eagle owl population: lessons for conservation. – *Biol. Conserv.* 143: 1911–1918.
- Schorcht, W., Bontadina, F. and Schaub, M. 2009. Variation of adult survival drives population dynamics in a migrating forest bat. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 78: 1182–1190.
- Shrubb, M. 1980. Farming influences on the food and hunting of kestrels. *Bird Study* 27: 109–115.
- Smart, J., Amar, A., Sim, I. M. W., Etheridge, B., Cameron, D., Christie, G. and Wilson, J. D. 2010. Illegal killing slows population recovery of a re-introduced raptor of high conservation concern – the red kite *Milvus milvus*. – *Biol. Conserv.* 143: 1278–1286.
- Stahl, J. T. and Oli, M. K. 2006. Relative importance of avian life-history variables to population growth rate. – *Ecol. Model.* 198: 23–39.
- Stearns, S. C. 1983. The influence of size and phylogeny on patterns of covariation among life-history traits in the mammals. – *Oikos* 41: 173–187.
- Tavecchia, G., Adrover, J., Navarro, A. M. and Pradel, R. 2012. Modeling mortality causes in longitudinal data in the presence of tag loss: application to raptor poisoning and electrocution. – *J. Appl. Ecol.* 49: 297–305.
- Tenan, S., Adrover, J., Navarro, A. M., Sergio, F. and Tavecchia, G. 2012. Demographic consequences of poison-related mortality in a threatened bird of prey. – *PLoS One* 7: e49187.
- Tenan, S., Becker, D., Tolkmitt, D. and Schaub, M. 2021. Decomposing fecundity and evaluating demographic influence of multiple broods in a migratory bird. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 90: 1071–1084.
- Traue, H. and Wuttky, K. 1966. Die Entwicklung des Rotmilans (*Milvus milvus* L.) vom Ei bis zum flügenden Vogel. – *Beiträge Vogelk.* 11: 253–275.
- Villafuente, R., Vinuela, J. and Blanco, J. C. 1998. Extensive predator persecution caused by population crash in a game species: the case of red kites and rabbits in Spain. – *Biol. Conserv.* 84: 181–188.
- Wahl, R. and Barbraud, C. 2014. The demography of a newly established osprey *Pandion haliaetus* population in France. – *Ibis* 156: 84–96.
- Walters, J. R., Crowder, L. B. and Priddy, J. A. 2002. Population viability analysis for red-cockaded woodpeckers using an individual-based model. – *Ecol. Appl.* 12: 249–260.
- Weegman, M. D., Bearhop, S., Fox, A. D., Hilton, G. M., Walsh, A. J., McDonald, J. L. and Hodgson, D. J. 2016. Integrated population modelling reveals a perceived source to be a cryptic sink. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 85: 467–475.
- Wiens, J. D., Noon, B. R. and Reynolds, R. T. 2006. Post-fledging survival of northern goshawks. The importance of prey abundance, weather and dispersal. – *Ecol. Appl.* 16: 406–418.
- Wilson, J. D., Whittingham, M. J. and Bradbury, R. B. 2005. The management of crop structure: a general approach to reversing the impacts of agricultural intensification on birds? – *Ibis* 147: 453–463.
- Zipkin, E. F. and Saunders, S. P. 2018. Synthesizing multiple data types for biological conservation using integrated population models. – *Biol. Conserv.* 217: 240–250.